

Student Railway Pass online Process

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the significance of Digitization of offline process which provides more advantages. The Digital India program is a flagship program of the Government of India with a vision to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. But there are still some government offices that still are using their old manual/offline process to do day to day work. Student Railway Concession pass is one of the offline process we want to make it online as it will save time & paper work.

Keywords: *Railway Concession Form, Monthly Student Pass, Online Railway Pass Form, mobile application.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Some government offices that still are using their old manual process to do day to day work. One of them is Railway IRCTC Mumbai. Every process Ticket Booking System is digitalized except the student concession form process. There are nearly 227 colleges in Mumbai and suburbs and more than 45k / 50k student apply for railway concession form. Every college has its own different process for applying railway concession form. Some college has online website to collect data of students and some colleges are still struggling with offline form process which takes more than 2-3 days or sometimes if office authority person is not available students have to wait for hours or sometimes even for many days to collect their forms with college stamp and signature of authority.

Either college provide online service to student to fill their form or fill it manually at the end student has to take that form to railway ticket counter and railway authority person do manual process to fill student

details and check student college id by that time to verify student details. It takes minimum 6-7 minutes to every student.

So, to save time and all the offline paper work of students, college and Railway authority I have solution that if we make this process digitalized it will save most of our time as well as at ticket counter and at college office.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

I have done online research to find online Mumbai local concession form

Here below are some reviews of questionnaires' I have got.

How do I avail Mumbai local train concession for students, online?

4 Answers

 Pankaj Patil, lives in Mumbai, Maharashtra, India
Answered Jul 19, 2017 · Author has 87 answers and 43.1k answer views

Online it's difficult. No provision till date

For other processess

<https://www.services.irctc.co.in...>

How do I avail students concession on train tickets?

Thanks

1.6k Views · Answer requested by Ishita Sailas

Figure 1: Online Question Answer About Student Concession

Patil Brijesh, lives in Mumbai, Maharashtra, India
 Answered Jan 10, 2017

I am not sure if this is available online However the institution where you are studying can give u a 50% concession form signed by principal which you can submit to any suburban ticket window and avail 50% discount on season ticket

1.1k Views - View Upvoters

Figure2: Online Question Answer About Student Concession

Somesh Babaria, lives in Mumbai, Maharashtra, India
 Answered Jan 10, 2017

I dont think its available online.

youll have to use the old ongoing process(getting the concession form from your college office) than you can avail the monthly or quarterly concession pass from the ticket counter.

1.5k Views - View Upvoters

Figure3: Online Question Answer About Student Concession

Aman Upadhyay, lived in Mumbai, Maharashtra, India
 Answered Jan 10, 2017 - Author has 103 answers and 80.5k answer views

You will have to enquire the school for any particular online portal of theirs that of it is available or not.

If not then too its not that tough a simple request letter usually is enough .

But some schools have forms which are to be filled and submitted and the give you a school certified certificate that you are eligible for concession and you can use that to get you concession pass .

Do ask if I haven't cleared your doubt .

Figure4: Online Question Answer About Student Concession

From Above Questionnaire's you will get the Clear Idea about the Scenario & How much its need to be implement as early as possible.

I also have conducted online survey & This is the response of other college students.

Does your college provide online form for student pass?

13 responses

Figure5: 30% of college provide form online

Do you think Offline process of Filling form and submitting to Railway counter is time consuming & Hectic? also include lot of paper work?

12 responses

Figure6: 91% of students think that offline process is hectic & time consuming

You want Student Pass process should be online?

13 responses

Figure7: 100% students think that these process should get online

III. Problem Definition

Offline Process makes it more slow and hectic as are in computer technology world. We hate to wait right? So, I guess everyone has face this process irritating as wo don't get our pass on time sometimes our college authority is not available to give us form or sometimes even after filling form we have to wait for our HOD/Principle signature and to print college stamp on it.

Some times when we lost our student pass we don't have another procedure to get back new one.

All these conclude to lots of paper work and lots of time consuming process.

Even after getting our form authorised by college we go and stand in front of railway authority to get our pass detail fill and then they give us pass. These is also time consuming or sometimes if the signature or college stamp is not proper printed on form they don't give us pass they return our form. Or cancel it.

IV. Solution to The Problem

Purpose of this research paper is that to make this railway concession form process to digitalize. We will create a mobile app to collect student data so every student can fill this form from their mobile phones.

It will be very convenient process for students to fill their form. By selecting their respective college name their data will sort & send to their college website.

Aadhar 14-digit PIN is mandatory for students to fill it in form for uniqueness.

After getting all this data that is to be verifying by college authority first and then send to Railway IRCTC Mumbai for further process.

To keep all this data unique student has to register in application with their **Aadhar PIN number**. So that after getting all the data from every colleges of Mumbai, railway authority won't face any trouble with student records.

And whenever student will go to collect their pass at ticket counter he/she has to give just **Aadhar PIN number** to railway authority.

And they will **fetch details** of **students** by their **Aadhar pin number** and take print give student pass within 2 /3minutes. No manually typing student data process at all. It will be easy and quick.

V. Conceptual Working of System

Step 1: Students will fill the form using mobile application, with basic information of Travelling route, 14-digit Aadhar PIN Which is Mandatory to make every student data unique & Their Respective College Name So that student data will be sort and sent to their respective college database.

Figure8: Students filling form using mobile application

Step 2: Now College Authority Will verify this data & Pass it to the Railway Authority (Railway Database).

Figure9: College Authority Verify & Pass data to the Railway Authority

Step 3: Now when the Student will go to the railway counter Then they just have to show their Aadhar id / or give Aadhar 14-digit PIN So that Railway ticket officer will retrieve their data from their database. & Make print of their pass and give it to the student within 2-3- minutes.

Figure10: Railway Ticket Officer will retrieve the data using student Aadhar pin.

Step 4: Now Student will get Pass

VI. FACTS AND FINDINGS

The merging of online technologies will help to improve efficient connectivity to internet so that it will be easier for every day to maintain database & keep data secure. This Application helps to improve by covering the drawbacks of Manual Process.

This Application has not yet been implemented yet but it has very useful effect over all colleges in Mumbai. It will help to make process fast and secure and can save time and lots of paper work.

VII. CONCLUSION

The idea of Application will get a wider scope, as it provides very efficient and alternate option over manual process. So, this paper concludes that Online Student Concession Pass is good for Every Student as well as Railway so that they can have all students' data who use the facility of railway.

If Mumbai University Apply This over all colleges in

Mumbai Then They can save Lots of Time & Paper Work.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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